

Healthcare Cost Analysis

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Abstract—This paper proposes a database system to overcome the limitations of storing, managing, and analyzing healthcare cost data in flat file formats such as Excel. The database system will provide better data integrity, consistency, security, and accessibility to analyze the healthcare cost data to make better decisions for the target users.

Keywords—BCNF, indexing, primary key, foreign key, healthcare, triggers

I. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Healthcare systems have complex financial indicators that can be difficult to understand, making it crucial to assess their performance. The dataset includes valuable data on healthcare services, patient outcomes, and patterns of service consumption. The current data storage format in Excel has limitations in data storage, management, and analysis, so a proposed database system will provide a centralized and efficient way to manage and store healthcare data. The system will also ensure data security, backup, and recovery features. Using a database system over Excel will provide better data integrity and consistency, efficient querying, and analysis of large datasets.

II. TARGET USER

This database should be administered by an expert in database management who then can help with setting proper security accesses around the database system. The database administrator will grant access to appropriate parties which then can consume the data to generate valuable insights.

The database administrator can also help with guiding the analysts or healthcare providers with writing efficient queries to the database. It will then be the responsibility of the analysts to provide the stakeholders with the insights gathered from the datasets. That would be the stakeholders or business leaders who would be making business decisions about their financial costs & metrics for the entire hospitals.

III. DATABASE DESIGNS

Dataset source:

<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/kanikakhera/healthcare-dataset>

Follow the readme.txt file in order to implement all the database functionalities and designs.

Following files are utilized from the link above from the Kaggle website:

1. Patient_history_samp.csv

The file is loaded directly to the patient_demographics table. New columns are added to this table after loading into the database via SQL.

2. Inpatient_Pat.csv:

The file is first loaded onto a temporary table. Normalization is applied to this & then using the temporary table, the 2 tables are loaded: drg_metrics & drg_procedures

3. Inpatient_provd.csv

The file is loaded directly into a temporary table temp_table. Once the temporary table has this data then we normalize this table into 2 different table called as inpatient_provider and inpatient_facility_drg_metrics. All the normalization is done using SQL, so do not have to edit the CSV file. Once these steps are completed the temporary table is dropped.

4. Outpatient_Pat.csv

The file is first loaded onto a temporary table. Normalization is applied to this & then using the temporary table, the 2 tables are loaded: apc_metrics and apc_procedures.

5. Outpatient_provd.csv

The file is loaded directly into a temporary table temp_table. This temporary table was first created via SQL. Once the temporary table has this data then we normalize this table into 2 different table sets called outpatient_provider and outpatient_facility_apc_metrics. All the normalization is done using SQL, so do not have to edit the CSV file. Once these steps are completed the temporary table is dropped.

To load the csv data into tables, copy command is utilized which eliminates the intervention of manual work in excel.

IV. NORMALIZATIONS

During this database design, we especially paid attention to BCNF to create tables and columns.

We utilized BCNF's formal definition in order to design our database structure: "A table is in BCNF if and only if every

non-trivial functional dependency in the table is a dependency on a candidate key.”

Using BCNF, it helped us in reducing the redundancy of data, helped us understand the database design more accurately & ensured us in improving the data integrity.

In our previous milestone, where BCNF was not implemented, our database design looked like this:

Issues:

1. In total we are utilizing 5 files to populate our tables. If we had utilized the 5 files directly and loaded them into the tables, then we would not have followed the normalization rules. The reason for this is because a single file contained data that did not follow 1NF, 2NF or any other rules.
2. APC & DRG column was utilized in the previous design where the APC & DRG column contained the definitions of their procedures which contained the name of the procedure as well as the primary key id inside a single column. This not only violated BCNF but also violated 1NF form.
3. Hospital Referral Region column was utilized inside the outpatient facility table which was also another violation because the hospital referral region was dependent on the provider id of that hospital.

These were the main problems which needed us to decompose the tables into our BCNF format.

Decomposition to BCNF:

1. The 5 files were separated and divided into a total of 9 tables together. These 9 tables now follow the BCNF decomposition.
2. APC & DRG columns which contained the definition of procedures and ID together were separated out. APC_ID and DRG_ID were created as the Primary Key IDs & a separate table for apc_procedures and drg_procedures were created in order to identify what was the name of the procedure performed.
3. The Hospital Referral Region column was moved to the provider’s table in order it to follow the proper BCNF decomposition rule.

V. DATA MODELS

A. Patient Demographics

Table Name: patient_demographics

File Name: patient_history_samp.csv

Description: Contains patient information such as age, gender, income, family income, race, blood type. This table follows BCNF as all the columns are dependent on its candidate key.

Number of Rows: 500,000

Schema:

Field	Key	Data Type	Constraints
pat_id	PK	bigint	Not Null
age		string (50)	Nullable
gender		string (20)	Nullable
income		string (50)	Nullable
family_income_class		string (50)	Nullable
race		string (50)	Nullable
blood_type		string (5)	Nullable

Attribute Description:

Column	Description
pat_id	This is the primary key of the patient. It is unique & can be used to a patient based on it. This column cannot be NULL
age	This describes the age group the patient belongs to
gender	Gender of the patient
income	This describes the income group of how much the patient earns
family_income_class	Family income of the patient
race	Race of the patient
blood_type	Blood type of the patient

B. Diagnosis Related Grouper Metrics

Table Name: drg_metrics

File Name: Inpatient_Pat.csv

Description: This table contains information about the diagnosis related grouper information and finance metrics related to it. This table follows BCNF as all the columns are dependent on its candidate key.

Number of Rows: 100

Schema:

Field	Key	Data Type	Constraints
drg_id	PK	string (500)	Not Null
services_performed		bigint	Nullable
average_covered_charges		double precision	Nullable
average_total_payments		double precision	Nullable
average_medicare_payments		double precision	Nullable

Attribute Description:

Column	Description
drg_id	This is the diagnosis related grouper id. This is the unique column thus PK to this table & cannot be NULL.

services_performed	This describes the total number of services performed on the patients
average_covered_charges	This describes the average covered charges for this DRG
average_total_payments	This describes the average total payments made for this DRG
average_medicare_payments	This describes the average medicare payments received for this DRG

C. Inpatient Providers

Table Name: inpatient_provider

File Name: Inpatient_provdr.csv

Description: This table provides information about the inpatient provider demographics. This table follows BCNF as all the columns are dependent on its candidate key.

Number of Rows: 3,337

Schema:

Field	Key	Data Type	Constraints
provider_id	PK	integer	Not Null
provider_hospital		string (150)	Nullable
hospital_referral_region		string (500)	Nullable
provider_street_address		string (500)	Nullable
provider_city		string (100)	Nullable
provider_state		string (50)	Nullable
provider_zipcode		integer	Nullable

Attribute Description:

Column	Description
provider_id	This is the unique provider id for the inpatient provider table. It cannot be NULL
provider_hospital	This is the name of the provider hospital/facility
hospital_referral_region	This is the region where the hospital belongs to
provider_street_address	This is the address of the facility
provider_city	This is the city where the facility is located
provider_state	This is the state where the facility is located
provider_zipcode	This is the zip code where the facility is located

D. Inpatient Facility & DRG Metrics

Table Name: inpatient_facility_drg_metrics

File Name: Inpatient_provdr.csv

Description: This table contains information about each of the inpatient facilities & the finance metrics related to it. This provides a description of inpatient services. This table follows BCNF as all the columns are dependent on its candidate key.

Number of Rows: 163,065

Foreign Key References:

foreign key (provider_id) references inpatient_provider (provider_id)

foreign key (drg_id) references drg_metrics (drg_id)

Schema:

Field	Key	Data Type	Constraints
drg_id	PK, FK	string (500)	Not Null
provider_id	PK, FK	integer	Not Null
total_discharges		integer	Nullable
average_covered_charges		double precision	Nullable
average_total_payments		double precision	Nullable
average_medicare_payments		double precision	Nullable

Attribute Description:

Column	Description
drg_id	This is the DRG ID – diagnosis related grouper. It is a PK to this table & cannot be NULL. This is also the foreign key to the drg_metrics table. Action - Drop Cascade for this constraint.
provider_id	This is the inpatient provider id. It cannot be NULL. It is the PK of this table & the foreign key to the inpatient_provider table. Action - Drop Cascade for this constraint.
total_discharges	Describes the total number of discharges that happened at that location
average_covered_charges	Describes the average covered charges for the DRG at that location
average_total_payments	Describes the average total payments made for the DRG at that location
average_medicare_payments	Describes the average medicare payments received for the DRG at that location

E. APC Metrics

Table Name: apc_metrics

File Name: Outpatient_pat.csv

Description: This table contains information about the Ambulatory Payment Classifications (APC) & the finance metrics related to it. This provides a description of outpatient services. This table follows BCNF as all the columns are dependent on its candidate key.

Number of Rows: 30

Schema:

Field	Key	Data Type	Constraints
apc_id	PK	integer	Nullable
services_performed		integer	Nullable
average_estimated_submitted_charges		double precision	Nullable
average_total_payments		double precision	Nullable

Attribute Description:

Column	Description
apc_id	This describes the procedure id of the APC. This is a unique

column, PK to this table & thus cannot be NULL

services_performed	These are the number of services performed for this procedure
average_estimated_submitted_charges	This is the average estimated charges that were submitted for this procedure
average_total_payments	This is the average total payments made for this procedure

F. Outpatient Providers

Table Name: outpatient_provider

File Name: Outpatient_provdr.csv

Description: This table provides information about the outpatient provider demographics. This table follows BCNF as all the columns are dependent on its candidate key.

Number of Rows: 3,135

Schema:

Field	Key	Data Type	Constraints
provider_id	PK	integer	Not Null
provider_hospital		string (150)	Nullable
hospital_referral_region		string (500)	Nullable
provider_street_address		string (500)	Nullable
provider_city		string (100)	Nullable
provider_state		string (50)	Nullable
provider_zip_code		integer	Nullable

Attribute Description:

Column	Description
provider_id	This is the unique provider id for the outpatient provider table. It cannot be NULL
provider_hospital	This is the name of the provider hospital/facility
hospital_referral_region	This is the region where the hospital belongs to
provider_street_address	This is the address of the facility
provider_city	This is the city where the facility is located
provider_state	This is the state where the facility is located
provider_zipcode	This is the zip code where the facility is located

G. Outpatient Facility and APC Metrics

Table Name: outpatient_facility_apc_metrics

File Name: Outpatient_provdr.csv

Description: This table contains information about each of the hospital Ambulatory Payment Classifications (APC) & the finance metrics related to it. This provides a description of outpatient services. This table follows BCNF as all the columns are dependent on its candidate key.

Number of Rows: 43,372

Foreign Key References:

foreign key (provider_id) references outpatient_provider (provider_id),

foreign key (apc_id) references apc_metrics (apc_id)

Schema:

Field	Key	Data Type	Constraints
apc_id	PK, FK	integer	Not Null
provider_id	PK, FK	integer	Not Null
services_performed		integer	Nullable
average_estimated_submitted_charges		double precision	Nullable
average_total_payments		double precision	Nullable

Attribute Description:

Column	Description
apc_id	This is the unique value that describes the procedure ID performed at the outpatient facility. It is a PK to this table & cannot be NULL. This is also the foreign key to the apc_metrics table. Action - Drop Cascade for this constraint.
provider_id	This is the provider id. It cannot be NULL and is the PK & the FK to the outpatient_provider table. Action - Drop Cascade for this constraint.
services_performed	Number of outpatient services performed at that location
average_estimated_submitted_charges	Describes the average estimated charges submitted for the APC at that location
average_total_payments	Describes the average total payments made for the APC at that location

H. APC Procedures

Table Name: apc_procedures

File Name: Outpatient_pat.csv

Description: This table contains the name of the Ambulatory Payment Classifications (APC) & its APC ID

Number of Rows: 30

Schema:

Field	Key	Data Type	Constraints
apc_id	PK	integer	Not Null
apc_procedure_name		string (500)	Nullable

Attribute Description:

Column	Description
apc_id	This describes the procedure id of the APC. This is a unique column, PK to this table & thus cannot be NULL
apc_procedure_name	This is the name of the APC Procedure

I. DRG Procedures

Table Name: drg_procedures

File Name: Inpatient_pat.csv

Description: This table contains the name of the Diagnosis Related Grouper (DRG) & its DRG ID.

Number of Rows: 30

Schema:

Field	Key	Data Type	Constraints
drg_id	PK	integer	Not Null
drg_procedure_name		string (500)	Nullable

Attribute Description:

Column	Description
drg_id	DRG id unique column thus PK & cannot be NULL.
drg_procedure_name	This is the name of the DRG Procedure

VI. TRIGGERS & INDEXES

Triggers: They are used so that automatic execution of SQL commands can happen when an events, such as insertions, updates, or deletions of data in a table. They are commonly used for enforcing data integrity, auditing changes, cascading updates, synchronizing data, and implementing business logic.

This database has been added with 2 Triggers:

- **set_default_blood_type:** A trigger has been added on patient_demographics table in order to keep the integrity of the blood_type column in it. If a new record is added to this table that contains NULL data for blood_type then a value of 'NA' is added automatically using this trigger.
- **set_default_race:** This is the other trigger that has been added on patient_demographics table in order to keep the integrity of the race column. If a new record is added to this table that contains the value as 'Not Specified' then a value of NULL is added automatically using this trigger.

Indexes: Indexes in SQL are used to improve the performance of database queries by allowing the database engine to quickly locate the rows in a table that match the search criteria. They work by creating a data structure that contains a copy of the indexed columns in sorted order, which makes it faster to search for specific values or ranges of values. Indexes are commonly used in large tables where searching for data without an index could be slow and inefficient.

This database has been added with 3 Indexes to improve performance of the queries as these columns & tables are used often and contains lots of records

Index Name: idx_drg_metrics_services_performed

Table Name: drg_metrics

Column Name: services_performed

Index Name: idx_apc_metrics_services_performed

Table Name: apc_metrics

Column Name: services_performed

Index Name: idx_patient_demographics_income

Table Name: patient_demographics

Column Name: income

```
CREATE INDEX idx_drg_metrics_services_performed
ON drg_metrics (services_performed);
```

```
CREATE INDEX idx_apc_metrics_services_performed
ON apc_metrics (services_performed);
```

```
CREATE INDEX idx_patient_demographics_income
ON patient_demographics (income);
```

This one query used to run longer than usual. It was estimated that it ran for about an average of 68ms, but once an index was utilized, it increased the speed even more to about 58 ms.

Before using index:

```
7 select
8   drg_metrics.drg_id,
9   drg_procedures.drg_procedure_name,
10  drg_metrics.services_performed,
11  ROW_NUMBER() OVER(ORDER BY drg_metrics.services_performed desc) rank_of_drg_procedure
12 from
13   drg_metrics
14   inner join drg_procedures on drg_procedures.drg_id = drg_metrics.drg_id
15 order by
16   rank_of_drg_procedure;
```

Data Output Messages Notifications
Successfully run. Total query runtime: 68 msec.
100 rows affected.

After using index:

```
7 select
8   drg_metrics.drg_id,
9   drg_procedures.drg_procedure_name,
10  drg_metrics.services_performed,
11  ROW_NUMBER() OVER(ORDER BY drg_metrics.services_performed desc) rank_of_drg_procedure
12 from
13   drg_metrics
14   inner join drg_procedures on drg_procedures.drg_id = drg_metrics.drg_id
15 order by
16   rank_of_drg_procedure;
```

Data Output Messages Notifications
Successfully run. Total query runtime: 59 msec.
100 rows affected.

VII. QUERIES

After creating the indexes, triggers. We queried our database to find out some data related to the metrics, providers, procedures in order to gain information of how hospitals finances are managed as well gained information about some of the patient demographics,

Here are some of the questions we tried to answer using our queries. While answering the questions, we used different types of sql statements like "sub query", "cte", "joins", "group by", "order by", "row_number", "counts", "sum" in order to find our information.

1. Find the inpatient provider details which has received the most average total payments made for the DRG procedure
2. Find the outpatient provider details which has performed the least services
3. Rank the drg procedures in the descending order of their total procedures performed.
4. Find out the provider_id which perform services at inpatient facility but not on the outpatient facility and has services performed greater than 200
5. Based on the patient data, find out the distribution of patient's income
6. Find out the total amount of money together an inpatient facility and outpatient facility has received from the patients
7. Find the apc procedure which is least performed
8. Find the name of the hospital referral region which has the presence of most hospitals.

Create Tables, Primary Keys, Foreign Keys, References:

```
CREATE TABLE public.inpatient_facility_drg_metrics
(
    drg_id bigint NOT NULL,
    provider_id integer NOT NULL,
    services_performed integer,
    average_covered_charges double precision,
    average_total_payments double precision,
    average_medicare_payments double precision,
    PRIMARY KEY (drg_id, provider_id),
    FOREIGN KEY (provider_id) REFERENCES inpatient_provider(provider_id),
    FOREIGN KEY (drg_id) REFERENCES drg_metrics(drg_id),
    FOREIGN KEY (drg_id) REFERENCES drg_procedures(drg_id)
);
```

Insert:

```
insert into patient_demographics (
    pat_id,
    age,
    gender,
    income,
    family_income_class,
    race,
    blood_type
)
VALUES (
    6,
    '<65',
    'F',
    '<16000',
    'lower income',
    'Other',
    NULL
);
```

Update, Case Statements, Random:

```
update patient_demographics
set family_income_class=
    case
        when random() < 0.1 then 'lower income'
        when random() < 0.2 then 'medium income'
        when random() < 0.4 then 'upper income'
        when random() < 0.6 then 'medium income'
        when random() < 0.8 then 'lower income'
        else NULL
    end
;
```

Delete:

```
delete from patient_demographics
where income is NULL;
```

Alter:

```
ALTER TABLE IF EXISTS public.temp_table
OWNER to postgres;
```

Copy:

```
copy public.patient_demographics
(
    pat_id, age, gender, income
)
FROM 'D:/vaibhav/USA/Bufalo/Spring 2023/CSE 500/Project/Datasets/health_care_dataset/patient_history_samp.csv'
DELIMITER ',' CSV HEADER;
```

Drop, If exists, Cascade:

```
drop index if exists idx_drg_metrics_services_performed;
drop index if exists idx_apc_metrics_services_performed;
drop index if exists idx_patient_demographics_income;

drop function if exists set_default_blood_type cascade;
drop function if exists set_default_race cascade;

drop trigger if exists set_default_blood_type_trigger on patient_demographics;
drop trigger if exists set_default_race_trigger on patient_demographics;
```

Index:

```
CREATE INDEX idx_drg_metrics_services_performed
ON drg_metrics (services_performed);

CREATE INDEX idx_apc_metrics_services_performed
ON apc_metrics (services_performed);

CREATE INDEX idx_patient_demographics_income
ON patient_demographics (income);
```

Triggers & Functions:

```
CREATE OR REPLACE FUNCTION set_default_race()
RETURNS TRIGGER AS $$
BEGIN
    IF NEW.race = 'Not Specified' THEN
        NEW.race := NULL;
    END IF;

    RETURN NEW;
END;
$$ LANGUAGE plpgsql;

CREATE OR REPLACE TRIGGER set_default_race_trigger
BEFORE INSERT ON patient_demographics
FOR EACH ROW
EXECUTE FUNCTION set_default_race();
```

Select, Sub-Query, Sum, Union all:

```
select
    sum(total_payments) as total_amount_received
from
(
    select
        sum(average_total_payments) as total_payments
    from
        apc_metrics
    union all
    select
        sum(average_total_payments) as total_payments
    from
        drg_metrics
) as a;
```

Where, Left Joins, Group By & Having:

```
select
    inpatient_facility_drg_metrics.provider_id,
    sum(inpatient_facility_drg_metrics.services_performed) as total_services_performed
from
    inpatient_facility_drg_metrics
left join outpatient_facility_apc_metrics
    on inpatient_facility_drg_metrics.provider_id = outpatient_facility_apc_metrics.provider_id
where
    outpatient_facility_apc_metrics.provider_id is null
group by
    inpatient_facility_drg_metrics.provider_id
having
    sum(inpatient_facility_drg_metrics.services_performed) > 200;
```

CTE, Limit, Order By:

```
with provider_id_cte as
(
  select
    ip.provider_id,
    sum(iffd.average_total_payments) as sum_average_total_payments
  from
    inpatient_provider as ip
  inner join inpatient_facility_drg_metrics as iff on iff.provider_id = ip.provider_id
  group by
    ip.provider_id
  order by
    sum_average_total_payments desc
  limit 1
)
select
  ip.*
from
  inpatient_provider as ip
  inner join provider_id_cte as pi on pi.provider_id = ip.provider_id ;
```

Inner Join & Row Number:

```
select
  drg_metrics.drg_id,
  drg_procedures.drg_procedure_name,
  drg_metrics.services_performed,
  ROW_NUMBER() OVER(ORDER BY drg_metrics.services_performed desc) rank_of_drg_procedure
from
  drg_metrics
  inner join drg_procedures on drg_procedures.drg_id = drg_metrics.drg_id
order by
  rank_of_drg_procedure;
```

Counts:

```
select
  hospital_referral_region,
  count(hospital_referral_region) as count_hospital_referral_region
from
  inpatient_provider
group by
  hospital_referral_region
order by count_hospital_referral_region desc
```

VIII. EXPLAIN

Explain is a SQL command used to obtain information about how the database engine will execute a specific SQL statement & its cost associated with a particular statement.

When a SQL statement is executed, the database engine creates a query plan, which is a set of steps used to retrieve the requested data.

The explain tool can be used in order to identify if a query is running longer and if it can be optimized.

We utilized explain in find the following things:

- Find out our problematic queries & perform analysis on them
- Find how indexing helped in query performance & analysis of them.

Below, we will talk about 3 problematic queries we came across & the analysis we performed using explain & the solutions we think that can benefit the performance of the query.

Question 1: Find the outpatient provider details which has performed the least services

Problematic Query:

```
with provider_id_cte as
(
  select
    op.provider_id,
    sum(ofa.services_performed) as total_services_performed
  from
    outpatient_provider as op
  inner join outpatient_facility_apc_metrics as ofa on ofa.provider_id = op.provider_id
  group by
    op.provider_id
  order by
    total_services_performed asc
  limit 1
)
select
  op.*
from
  outpatient_provider as op
  inner join provider_id_cte as pi on pi.provider_id = op.provider_id ;
```

Explain Query Plan:

QUERY PLAN	text
1	Nested Loop (cost=1286.43..1294.46 rows=1 width=78)
2	-> Limit (cost=1286.15..1286.15 rows=1 width=12)
3	-> Sort (cost=1286.15..1293.99 rows=3135 width=12)
4	Sort Key: (sum(ofa.services_performed))
5	-> HashAggregate (cost=1239.12..1270.47 rows=3135 width=8)
6	Group Key: op_1.provider_id
7	-> Hash Join (cost=155.54..1022.26 rows=43372 width=8)
8	Hash Cond: (ofa.provider_id = op_1.provider_id)
9	-> Seq Scan on outpatient_facility_apc_metrics ofa (cost=0.00..752.72 rows=43372 width=8)
10	-> Hash (cost=116.35..116.35 rows=3135 width=4)
11	-> Seq Scan on outpatient_provider op_1 (cost=0.00..116.35 rows=3135 width=4)
12	-> Index Scan using outpatient_provider_pkey on outpatient_provider op (cost=0.28..8.30 rows=1 width=7...)
13	Index Cond: (provider_id = op_1.provider_id)

Explain Graphical Analysis:

Analysis:

From this we see those 5 different functions like Hashes, Sorts, Limits, Joins are utilized inside the SQL, we can see cost associated with each of those functions.

Solution to improve performance:

Currently the query runs via a CTE and has a limit statement which is not an ideal way to run. There is more room for improvement in this query where we can get rid of some of the limit commands and some extra joins happening on the same tables. This way we can improve the performance of the query.

2. Find the apc procedure which is least performed

Problematic Query:

```
select
  *
from
  apc_procedures
where
  apc_id =
  (
    select
      apc_id
    from
      apc_metrics
    order by
      services_performed
    limit 1
  );
```

Explain Query Plan:

QUERY PLAN	text
1	Index Scan using apc_procedures_pkey on apc_procedures (cost=31.90..39.92 rows=1 width=5...)
2	Index Cond: (apc_id = \$0)
3	InitPlan 1 (returns \$0)
4	-> Limit (cost=31.75..31.75 rows=1 width=12)
5	-> Sort (cost=31.75..35.38 rows=1450 width=12)
6	Sort Key: apc_metrics.services_performed
7	-> Seq Scan on apc_metrics (cost=0.00..24.50 rows=1450 width=12)

Explain Graphical Analysis:

Analysis:

In this query, we are utilizing the limit function which seems to be problematic as it is imposing cost on the query. Along with limit, we also seem to be utilizing sort functionality which again is hurting the query performance.

Solution to improve performance:

Utilizing indexes on the services_performed column will definitely help in making this query run faster. We are also using limit and order by, if we can find a way to avoid limit and sort functionality, the query performance can improve more.

3. Find the inpatient provider details which has received the most average total payments made for the DRG procedure.

Problematic Query:

```
with provider_id_cte as
(
  select
  ip.provider_id,
  sum(ifd.average_total_payments) as sum_average_total_payments
  from
  inpatient_provider as ip
  inner join inpatient_facility_drg_metrics as ifd on ifd.provider_id = ip.provider_id
  group by
  ip.provider_id
  order by
  sum_average_total_payments desc
  limit 1
)
select
ip.*
from
inpatient_provider as ip
inner join provider_id_cte as pi on pi.provider_id = ip.provider_id ;
```

Explain Query Plan:

QUERY PLAN
1 Nested Loop (cost=4405.98..4414.02 rows=1 width=79)
2 -> Limit (cost=4405.70..4405.71 rows=1 width=12)
3 -> Sort (cost=4405.70..4414.05 rows=3337 width=12)
4 Sort Key: (sum(ifd.average_total_payments)) DESC
5 -> HashAggregate (cost=4355.65..4389.02 rows=3337 width=12)
6 Group Key: ip_1.provider_id
7 -> Hash Join (cost=122.08..3540.32 rows=163065 width=12)
8 Hash Cond: (ifd.provider_id = ip_1.provider_id)
9 -> Seq Scan on inpatient_facility_drg_metrics ifd (cost=0.00..2989.65 rows=163065 width=12)
10 -> Hash (cost=80.37..80.37 rows=3337 width=4)
11 -> Seq Scan on inpatient_provider ip_1 (cost=0.00..80.37 rows=3337 width=4)
12 -> Index Scan using inpatient_provider_pkey on inpatient_provider ip (cost=0.28..8.30 rows=1 width=79)
13 Index Cond: (provider_id = ip_1.provider_id)

Explain Graphical Analysis:

Analysis:

In this query there are multiple functionalities being used like hashes, aggregate, sorter, limits, and nested loop joins. This is definitely hurting our query as we seem to be using the joins on the same table twice.

Solution to improve performance:

We will need to simplify the query even more. If we can utilize a sub query or some other SQL function or use more indexing, then this helps a bit more.

Avoiding sorters and limits and avoiding rejoining on the same table are other ways to improve query performance.

IX. PRODUCT

Website Creation :

The website performs CRUD operations.

The image of the web page shows the space to insert the patient records into the patient’s demographic table.

This web page can also perform delete and edit operations on the records of the table.

A form gets enabled to perform the update operation on the table when the edit button is clicked.

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REFERENCES

https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/kanikakhera/healthcare-dataset?select=Patient_history_samp.csv

CONTRIBUTION

Both the 2 of us in the project went above and beyond in developing this project and the report. Each of us targeted specific parts of the projects and provided their contributions in order to complete it.

Vaibhav Borkar:

Contributions:

- Database Design
- Implementation of the queries, indexes, triggers
- Normalization
- Report

Shilpitha Prasad Velamati:

Contributions:

- UI development for the website
- CRUD operations for the website
- Report